

Network Meta-Analysis using R package netmeta

Guido Schwarzer, Gerta Rücker

Institute of Medical Biometry and Statistics, Faculty of Medicine and Medical Center - University of Freiburg, Germany

guido.schwarzer@uniklinik-freiburg.de

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7777991>

ESMARConf 2023

Outline

Indirect Comparisons / Bucher Method

Mixed Treatment Comparison

Network Meta-Analysis Model

Network Meta-Analysis using R Package **netmeta**

The Results of Direct and Indirect Treatment Comparisons in Meta-Analysis of Randomized Controlled Trials

Heiner C. Bucher, Gordon H. Guyatt, Lauren E. Griffith, and Stephen D. Walter*

- Common approach in the 1990s for indirect comparisons: compare results from active treatment arms only
→ no advantage over non-randomized comparisons for results from randomized controlled trials (RCTs) and prone to bias
- Proposed approach: compare differences between active treatment and placebo in two sets of RCTs (comparing A and B, respectively, with placebo)
- Evaluation of differences between direct and indirect evidence
- No formal combination of direct and indirect evidence conducted

Diabetes Dataset

Network meta-analysis of diabetes treatments (Senn et al., 2013)

- 10 diabetes treatments
- 26 studies (1 three-arm study, 25 two-arm studies)
- Outcome: HbA1c (measured as mean change or mean post treatment value)
- Dataset is part of R package **netmeta**

For the moment, primary interest to compare Rosiglitazone and Metformin

- Two studies compare Rosiglitazone and Metformin directly
- Six studies compare Rosiglitazone with Placebo
- Four studies compare Metformin with Placebo

Direct and Indirect Evidence (Bucher et al., 1997)

Direct estimates (from three pairwise meta-analyses):

- $\hat{\theta}_{RP}^{direct}$ from six studies comparing Rosiglitazone and Placebo
- $\hat{\theta}_{MP}^{direct}$ from four studies comparing Metformin and Placebo
- $\hat{\theta}_{RM}^{direct}$ from two studies comparing Rosiglitazone and Metformin

Indirect estimate for the comparison Rosiglitazone minus Metformin (difference of pairwise treatment differences $R - P$ and $M - P$):

$$\hat{\theta}_{RM}^{indirect} = \hat{\theta}_{RP}^{direct} - \hat{\theta}_{MP}^{direct}$$

Pairwise Meta-Analyses

```
library("meta")
# Default settings for R session: (i) print results with two digits
# and (ii) no common effect model
settings.meta(digits = 2, common = FALSE)
data(Senn2013, package = "netmeta")
m1 <- metagen(TE, seTE, studlab = studlab, sm = "MD",
  data = Senn2013, subgroup = paste(treat1.long, treat2.long, sep = " vs "),
  overall = FALSE, overall.hetstat = FALSE, test.subgroup = FALSE,
  print.subgroup.name = FALSE)
print(update(m1,
  subset = treat1 %in% c("metf", "rosi") & treat2 %in% c("metf", "plac")),
  details = FALSE)

## Number of studies: k = 12
##
## Results for subgroups (random effects model):
##
##           k      MD      95%-CI  tau^2    tau    Q    I^2
## Metformin vs Placebo    4 -1.13 [-1.77; -0.49] 0.3479 0.5898 42.18 92.9%
## Rosiglitazone vs Placebo 6 -1.18 [-1.39; -0.96] 0.0518 0.2276 21.27 76.5%
## Rosiglitazone vs Metformin 2 -0.07 [-0.39; 0.24] 0      0      0.19 0.0%
```

• Direct estimate: $\hat{\theta}_{RM}^{direct} = -0.07$

• Indirect estimate: $\hat{\theta}_{RM}^{indirect} = -1.18 - (-1.13) = -0.05$

Pairwise Meta-Analyses – Common τ^2

```
# Update meta-analysis:  
# - change definition of subset  
# - assume a common between-study variance in pairwise comparisons  
print(update(m1, subset = treat1 %in% c("metf", "rosi") & treat2 == "plac",  
  tau.common = TRUE),  
  details = FALSE)
```

```
## Number of studies: k = 10
```

```
##
```

```
## Results for subgroups (random effects model):
```

```
##           k      MD      95%-CI  tau^2    tau    Q    I^2  
## Metformin vs Placebo  4 -1.17 [-1.61; -0.73] 0.1391 0.3730 42.18 92.9%  
## Rosiglitazone vs Placebo  6 -1.18 [-1.50; -0.86] 0.1391 0.3730 21.27 76.5%
```

- Direct estimate: $\hat{\theta}_{RM}^{direct} = -0.07$
- Indirect estimate: $\hat{\theta}_{RM}^{indirect} = -1.18 - (-1.17) = -0.01$

Network Meta-Analysis (*R-P* & *M-P* Studies)

- Same results conducting a network meta-analysis of studies comparing Rosiglitazone or Metformin with Placebo (*R-P* and *M-P* Studies)

```
library("netmeta")
```

```
# Note, some defaults defined with settings.meta() are also considered  
# for network meta-analyses.  
# See help pages of netmeta() and gs() for get settings.
```

```
data(Senn2013)
```

```
# Network meta-analysis with  
# - REML estimator for tau2 (default is DerSimonian-Laird)  
# - placebo as reference in printouts and forest plots  
# - sequence in printouts: Rosiglitazone, Metformin, Placebo  
net1 <- netmeta(TE, seTE, treat1.long, treat2.long, studlab, data = Senn2013,  
  subset = treat1 %in% c("metf", "rosi") & treat2 == "plac", sm = "MD",  
  method.tau = "REML", reference.group = "P", seq = c("R", "M", "P"))
```

Network Graph (*R-P* & *M-P* Studies)

```
netgraph(net1, number = TRUE, cex = 1.25, cex.number = 1.5)
```


Results for Direct Comparisons (*R-P* & *M-P* Studies)

```
net1

## Number of studies: k = 10
## Number of pairwise comparisons: m = 10
## Number of treatments: n = 3
## Number of designs: d = 2
##
## Random effects model
##
## Treatment estimate (sm = 'MD', comparison: other treatments vs 'Placebo'):
##           MD           95%-CI      z  p-value
## Rosiglitazone -1.18 [-1.50; -0.86] -7.23 < 0.0001
## Metformin      -1.17 [-1.61; -0.73] -5.18 < 0.0001
## Placebo        .           .           .           .
##
## Quantifying heterogeneity / inconsistency:
## tau^2 = 0.1391; tau = 0.3730; I^2 = 87.4% [78.2%; 92.7%]
##
## Tests of heterogeneity (within designs) and inconsistency (between designs):
##           Q  d.f.  p-value
## Total      63.45   8 < 0.0001
## Within designs 63.45   8 < 0.0001
## Between designs 0.00   0      --
```

Indirect Evidence – Variance Estimate

Assumption:

- Individual treatment estimates are independent (caveat: multi-arm studies, i.e., studies with more than two treatment arms!)

Variance estimate of indirect treatment estimate:

$$\widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{\theta}_{RM}^{\text{indirect}}) = \widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{\theta}_{RP}^{\text{direct}}) + \widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{\theta}_{MP}^{\text{direct}})$$

Direct and Indirect Evidence (*R-P* & *M-P* Studies)

```
netleague(net1)

## League table (random effects model):
##
##          Rosiglitazone          . -1.18 [-1.50; -0.86]
## -0.01 [-0.56; 0.54]          Metformin -1.17 [-1.61; -0.73]
## -1.18 [-1.50; -0.86] -1.17 [-1.61; -0.73]          Placebo
```

Elements on lower triangle

- correspond to network estimates (column vs row) with **direct** evidence for comparisons *R-P* and *M-P* and **indirect** evidence for comparison *R-M*

Elements on upper triangle

- correspond to direct evidence from pairwise comparisons (row vs column) with missing pairwise comparison *R-M* indicated by “.”

Mixed Treatment Comparison

- Direct evidence $\hat{\theta}_{RM}^{direct}$ ignored to calculate indirect treatment effect
- Next step: combine direct and indirect evidence

- Combined / mixed treatment estimate:

$$\hat{\theta}_{RM}^{combined} = \frac{w_{RM}^{direct} \hat{\theta}_{RM}^{direct} + w_{RM}^{indirect} \hat{\theta}_{RM}^{indirect}}{w_{RM}^{direct} + w_{RM}^{indirect}}$$

with

$$w_{RM}^{direct} = 1 / \widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{\theta}_{RM}^{direct}) \quad \text{and} \quad w_{RM}^{indirect} = 1 / \widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{\theta}_{RM}^{indirect})$$

Direct and Indirect Evidence (*R-P*, *M-P* & *M-R*)

```
net2 <- netmeta(TE, seTE, treat1.long, treat2.long, studlab, data = Senn2013,  
  sm = "MD", method.tau = "REML", ref = "P", seq = c("R", "M", "P"),  
  subset = treat1 %in% c("metf", "rosi") & treat2 %in% c("metf", "plac"))
```

```
netleague(net2)
```

```
## League table (random effects model):
```

```
##
```

```
##           Rosiglitazone -0.07 [-0.63; 0.49] -1.18 [-1.47; -0.89]
```

```
## -0.03 [-0.40; 0.34]           Metformin -1.18 [-1.59; -0.77]
```

```
## -1.19 [-1.46; -0.92] -1.16 [-1.50; -0.82]           Placebo
```

```
# Estimates of between-study variance
```

```
round(data.frame(net1 = net1$tau2, net2 = net2$tau2), 4)
```

```
##      net1    net2
```

```
## 1 0.1391 0.1101
```

Elements on lower triangle: mixed treatment estimates

Forest plot with direct, indirect and mixed treatment estimates:

```
forest(netsplit(net2, order = c("R", "M", "P")),  
  text.overall = "Mixed treatment estimate")
```

Direct, Indirect and Mixed Evidence

- Mixed estimates are typically more precise than the corresponding direct or indirect estimates
- More imprecise results under random effects model possible if
 - direct and indirect evidence disagree
 - larger heterogeneity exists in indirect evidence compared to direct evidence

Network Meta-Analysis – Aims and Assumptions

- **Aims**

- Combine direct and indirect evidence to get more precise estimates of treatment differences
- Include multi-arm studies in the analysis
- Rank treatments according to efficacy

- **Assumptions**

- The studies are independent
- The underlying effects are **consistent** (Salanti, 2012; Dias et al., 2013a)

- **Network consistency**

- The sum of direct treatment effects over all closed loops in the graph is zero
- Equivalent: The indirect evidence for the difference between any two treatments does not differ from the direct evidence
- Example three treatments A, B, C :

$$\theta_{AB}^{direct} = \theta_{AB}^{indirect} = \theta_{AC}^{direct} - \theta_{BC}^{direct}$$

Network Meta-Analysis Model – Design Matrix

Example with $n = 4$ treatments

- $\theta^{treat} = (\theta_A, \theta_B, \theta_C, \theta_D)$
- $k = 6$ studies (each providing a single pairwise comparison)
- $m = 6$ pairwise comparisons
- Pairwise comparisons – Design matrix:

$$\begin{array}{l} A \text{ vs } B : \\ A \text{ vs } B : \\ B \text{ vs } C : \\ C \text{ vs } D : \\ A \text{ vs } D : \\ B \text{ vs } D : \end{array} \begin{pmatrix} \hat{\theta}_1 \\ \hat{\theta}_2 \\ \hat{\theta}_3 \\ \hat{\theta}_4 \\ \hat{\theta}_5 \\ \hat{\theta}_6 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \theta_A - \theta_B \\ \theta_A - \theta_B \\ \theta_B - \theta_C \\ \theta_C - \theta_D \\ \theta_A - \theta_D \\ \theta_B - \theta_D \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \epsilon_3 \\ \epsilon_4 \\ \epsilon_5 \\ \epsilon_6 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \theta_A \\ \theta_B \\ \theta_C \\ \theta_D \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \epsilon_3 \\ \epsilon_4 \\ \epsilon_5 \\ \epsilon_6 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\hat{\theta} = \mathbf{X}\theta^{treat} + \epsilon$$

Network Meta-Analysis Model (Rücker, 2012)

$$\hat{\theta} = \mathbf{X}\theta^{treat} + \epsilon$$

- m pairwise treatment comparisons (denoted by $\hat{\theta}$) with standard errors $s = (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_m)$
- Design matrix \mathbf{X} ($m \times n$) defined by network structure
- Diagonal matrix \mathbf{W} ($m \times m$) containing the inverse variance weights
 - Common effects model: $1/s_1^2, \dots, 1/s_m^2$
 - Random effects model: $1/(s_1^2 + \tau^2), \dots, 1/(s_m^2 + \tau^2)$, e.g., generalised DerSimonian-Laird estimate of τ^2 (Jackson et al., 2013)
- Network estimates $\hat{\theta}^{nma}$ (under consistency assumption!)

$$\hat{\theta}^{nma} = \mathbf{H}\hat{\theta}$$

with $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{X}(\mathbf{X}^T\mathbf{W}\mathbf{X})^+\mathbf{X}^T\mathbf{W}$ (known as *hat matrix* in regression)

- Interpretation:

Network estimates $\hat{\theta}^{nma}$ are **linear combinations of observed estimates $\hat{\theta}$** with coefficients coming from the rows of \mathbf{H}

Covariance Matrix and Heterogeneity Statistics

- Standard errors for the network estimates $\hat{\theta}^{nma}$ calculated from the variance-covariance matrix

$$\widehat{\text{Cov}}(\hat{\theta}^{nma}) = \mathbf{X}(\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{X})^{-1} \mathbf{X}^T$$

- Heterogeneity / inconsistency measured by generalised Q_{total} statistic

$$Q_{total} = (\hat{\theta} - \hat{\theta}^{nma})^T \mathbf{W} (\hat{\theta} - \hat{\theta}^{nma})$$

with degrees of freedom $df = \sum_i (i - 1)k_i - (n - 1)$ where k_i is the number of studies with i arms

- Heterogeneity statistic I^2 (Rücker and Schwarzer, 2014)

$$I^2 = 100 \times \max\left(\frac{Q_{total} - df}{Q_{total}}, 0\right) \%$$

Multi-Arm Studies – Need to Account for Dependency

A study with p arms has

- $\binom{p}{2}$ pairwise comparisons
- but only $p - 1$ independent comparisons / degrees of freedom (df)

```
data.frame(arms = p <- 2:5, comps = choose(p, 2), df = p - 1)
```

```
##   arms comps df
## 1     2     1  1
## 2     3     3  2
## 3     4     6  3
## 4     5    10  4
```

Four treatments ($p = 4$), three independent comparisons ($df = 3$):

Multi-Arm Studies – Adjustment Methods

Standard approach: Reduce dimension, i.e. drop comparisons

(Lu et al., 2011; White et al., 2012)

- Based on standard regression methodology
- For each multi-arm study, choose a study-specific reference treatment
- Consider only comparisons to the study-specific reference treatment
(‘basic parameters’)

Alternative approach: Reduce weights of all comparisons

(Rücker, 2012; Rücker and Schwarzer, 2014)

- Implemented in R package **netmeta**
- Based on electrical network methodology
- For each multi-arm study, adjust the standard errors appropriately

Comparison of Adjustment Approaches

Given a four-arm study with six comparisons,

we may cut off three of six comparisons:

or reduce all weights by 1/2 (on average):

Datasets

- 1 **Diabetes data** (Senn et al., 2013)
 - 10 diabetes treatments
 - 26 studies (1 three-arm study, 25 two-arm studies)
 - Outcome: HbA1c (measured as mean change or mean post treatment value)
 - Dataset is part of R package **netmeta**
- 2 **Smoking cessation data** (Higgins et al., 2012; Dias et al., 2013b)
 - Four interventions for smoking cessation
 - 24 studies (2 three-arm studies, 22 two-arm studies)
 - Outcome: smoking stopped (binary outcome)
 - Dataset is part of R package **netmeta**
- 3 **Acute mania data** (Cipriani et al., 2011)
 - 14 treatments for acute mania
 - 47 studies (11 three-arm studies, 36 two-arm studies)
 - Outcome: response to treatment (binary outcome)
 - Excel file available

Diabetes Dataset

```
# Load diabetes dataset
data(Senn2013, package = "netmeta")
# Look at data of three studies
subset(Senn2013, studlab %in% c("DeFronzo1995", "Lewin2007", "Willms1999"))
```

##	TE	seTE	treat1.long	treat2.long	treat1	treat2	studlab
## 1	-1.90	0.1414	Metformin	Placebo	metf	plac	DeFronzo1995
## 2	-0.82	0.0992	Metformin	Placebo	metf	plac	Lewin2007
## 3	-0.20	0.3579	Metformin	Acarbose	metf	acar	Willms1999
## 27	-1.20	0.3758	Metformin	Placebo	metf	plac	Willms1999
## 28	-1.00	0.4669	Acarbose	Placebo	acar	plac	Willms1999

- Each row corresponds to a pairwise comparison (contrast-based format):
 - TE: mean difference (HbA1c), i.e., $\hat{\theta} = (\hat{\theta}_1, \dots, \hat{\theta}_{28}) = (\theta_{MP}, \dots, \theta_{AP}) + \epsilon$
 - seTE: standard error of mean difference, i.e., $s = (s_1, \dots, s_{28})$
- Treatment labels must be equal to identify treatments (no additional spaces)
- Willms1999 is a three-arm study contributing three pairwise comparisons
- Study labels **must be equal** to identify multi-arm studies!

Diabetes Dataset – Network Meta-Analysis

```
net3 <- netmeta(TE, seTE, treat1.long, treat2.long, studlab,  
  data = Senn2013, sm = "MD", method.tau = "REML",  
  reference.group = "plac")
```

The first four arguments with treatment estimates $\hat{\theta}$, standard errors s and treatment labels for pairwise comparisons are mandatory

Argument 5 providing study labels is mandatory for network meta-analyses with multi-arm studies

By default, first alphanumeric treatment (here: acarbose) would be used as reference treatment in printouts and plots, but we want to use placebo as reference

Main Results of Network Meta-Analysis (I)

net3

```
## Number of studies: k = 26
## Number of pairwise comparisons: m = 28
## Number of treatments: n = 10
## Number of designs: d = 15
##
## Random effects model
##
## Treatment estimate (sm = 'MD', comparison: other treatments vs 'Placebo'):
```

	MD	95%-CI	z	p-value
## Acarbose	-0.84	[-1.31; -0.37]	-3.51	0.0004
## Benfluorex	-0.74	[-1.28; -0.19]	-2.64	0.0083
## Metformin	-1.13	[-1.42; -0.83]	-7.52	< 0.0001
## Miglitol	-0.95	[-1.39; -0.51]	-4.20	< 0.0001
## Pioglitazone	-1.13	[-1.55; -0.71]	-5.30	< 0.0001
Placebo
## Rosiglitazone	-1.23	[-1.48; -0.99]	-9.95	< 0.0001
## Sitagliptin	-0.57	[-1.24; 0.10]	-1.66	0.0966
## Sulfonylurea	-0.42	[-0.88; 0.04]	-1.79	0.0741
## Vildagliptin	-0.70	[-1.37; -0.03]	-2.04	0.0409
## ...				

Main Results of Network Meta-Analysis (II)

```
net3
```

```
## ...  
## Quantifying heterogeneity / inconsistency:  
## tau^2 = 0.1011; tau = 0.3179; I^2 = 81.4% [72.0%; 87.7%]  
##  
## Tests of heterogeneity (within designs) and inconsistency (between designs):  
##           Q d.f.  p-value  
## Total           96.99   18 < 0.0001  
## Within designs  74.46   11 < 0.0001  
## Between designs 22.53    7  0.0021
```

Detailed Network Meta-Analysis Results (I)

```
print(summary(net3),
  truncate = studlab %in% c("DeFronzo1995", "Lewin2007", "Willms1999"),
  reference.group = "", all.treatments = TRUE, nchar.trts = 4)

## Original data (with adjusted standard errors for multi-arm studies):
##
##          treat1 treat2    TE   seTE seTE.adj narms multiarm
## DeFronzo1995  Metf   Plac -1.90 0.1414  0.3479    2
## Lewin2007     Metf   Plac -0.82 0.0992  0.3330    2
## Willms1999    Acar   Metf  0.20 0.3579  0.5471    3      *
## Willms1999    Metf   Plac -1.20 0.3758  0.5701    3      *
## Willms1999    Acar   Plac -1.00 0.4669  0.8078    3      *
## *** Output truncated ***
##
## Number of treatment arms (by study):
##          narms
## DeFronzo1995    2
## Lewin2007       2
## Willms1999      3
## *** Output truncated ***
## ...
```

Detailed Network Meta-Analysis Results (II)

```
## ...
## Results (random effects model):
##
##           treat1 treat2    MD      95%-CI
## DeFronzo1995  Metf   Plac -1.13 [-1.42; -0.83]
## Lewin2007     Metf   Plac -1.13 [-1.42; -0.83]
## Willms1999    Acar   Metf  0.29 [-0.21;  0.78]
## Willms1999    Metf   Plac -1.13 [-1.42; -0.83]
## Willms1999    Acar   Plac -0.84 [-1.31; -0.37]
## *** Output truncated ***
##
## Number of studies: k = 26
## Number of pairwise comparisons: m = 28
## Number of treatments: n = 10
## Number of designs: d = 15
## ...
```

Detailed Network Meta-Analysis Results (III)

```
## ...
## Random effects model
##
## Treatment estimate (sm = 'MD'):
##      Acar  Benf  Metf  Migl  Piog  Plac  Rosi  Sita  Sulf  Vild
## Acar      . -0.11  0.29  0.11  0.29 -0.84  0.39 -0.27 -0.42 -0.14
## Benf  0.11      .  0.39  0.21  0.39 -0.74  0.50 -0.17 -0.32 -0.04
## Metf -0.29 -0.39      . -0.18  0.00 -1.13  0.11 -0.56 -0.71 -0.43
## Migl -0.11 -0.21  0.18      .  0.18 -0.95  0.28 -0.38 -0.53 -0.25
## Piog -0.29 -0.39 -0.00 -0.18      . -1.13  0.10 -0.56 -0.71 -0.43
## Plac  0.84  0.74  1.13  0.95  1.13      .  1.23  0.57  0.42  0.70
## Rosi -0.39 -0.50 -0.11 -0.28 -0.10 -1.23      . -0.66 -0.82 -0.53
## Sita  0.27  0.17  0.56  0.38  0.56 -0.57  0.66      . -0.15  0.13
## Sulf  0.42  0.32  0.71  0.53  0.71 -0.42  0.82  0.15      .  0.28
## Vild  0.14  0.04  0.43  0.25  0.43 -0.70  0.53 -0.13 -0.28      .
##
## Lower 95%-confidence limit:
##      Acar  Benf  Metf  Migl  Piog  Plac  Rosi  Sita  Sulf  Vild
## Acar      . -0.83 -0.21 -0.54 -0.31 -1.31 -0.10 -1.09 -0.93 -0.96
## Benf -0.61      . -0.23 -0.49 -0.29 -1.28 -0.10 -1.03 -1.03 -0.90
## Metf -0.78 -1.01      . -0.71 -0.43 -1.42 -0.21 -1.29 -1.16 -1.16
## ...
```

Detailed Network Meta-Analysis Results (IV)

```
## ...
## Quantifying heterogeneity / inconsistency:
## tau^2 = 0.1011; tau = 0.3179; I^2 = 81.4% [72.0%; 87.7%]
##
## Tests of heterogeneity (within designs) and inconsistency (between designs):
##           Q d.f.  p-value
## Total           96.99   18 < 0.0001
## Within designs  74.46   11 < 0.0001
## Between designs 22.53    7  0.0021
##
## Legend:
## Abbreviation Treatment name
##      Acar      Acarbose
##      Benf      Benfluorex
##      Metf      Metformin
##      Migl      Miglitol
##      Piog      Pioglitazone
##      Plac      Placebo
##      Rosi      Rosiglitazone
##      Sita      Sitagliptin
##      Sulf      Sulfonylurea
##      Vild      Vildagliptin
```

Diabetes Dataset – Forest Plot

`forest(net3)`

Smoking Cessation Dataset

```
# Load smoking cessation data
data(smokingcessation, package = "netmeta")
# Look at first rows
head(smokingcessation)
```

##	event1	n1	event2	n2	event3	n3	treat1	treat2	treat3
## 1	9	140	23	140	10	138	A	C	D
## 2	11	78	12	85	29	170	B	C	D
## 3	75	731	363	714	NA	NA	A	C	
## 4	2	106	9	205	NA	NA	A	C	
## 5	58	549	237	1561	NA	NA	A	C	
## 6	0	33	9	48	NA	NA	A	C	

- Each row contains all information for a single study (wide arm-based format)
- This dataset does not contain study information, e.g., author and year, however, this information is not necessary (study labels: 1, ..., 24)
- The first two studies are multi-arm studies (with three treatments)
- Use `pairwise` for transformation from arm-based to contrast-based format (necessary input format for `netmeta`)

Smoking Cessation Dataset – Transform Data

```
p1 <- pairwise(treat = list(treat1, treat2, treat3),  
event = list(event1, event2, event3), n = list(n1, n2, n3),  
data = smokingcessation, sm = "OR")
```

- Mandatory arguments for the arm-based format and binary outcomes: treatment labels, number of events, number of participants
- Internally, `metabin` from R package `meta` (Balduzzi et al., 2019) is called to calculate log odds ratios and corresponding standard errors

```
head(p1[, 1:9], 7)
```

##	TE	seTE	studlab	treat1	treat2	event1	n1	event2	n2
## 1	-1.051293027	0.4132432	1	A	C	9	140	23	140
## 2	-0.128527575	0.4759803	1	A	D	9	140	10	138
## 3	0.922765452	0.3997972	1	C	D	23	140	10	138
## 4	-0.001244555	0.4504070	2	B	C	11	78	12	85
## 5	-0.225333286	0.3839393	2	B	D	11	78	29	170
## 6	-0.224088731	0.3722995	2	C	D	12	85	29	170
## 7	-2.202289286	0.1430439	3	A	C	75	731	363	714

- TE: log odds ratios $\hat{\theta}$, seTE: standard errors s
- Rows 1-3 and 4-6 are from two three-arm studies

Smoking Cessation – Network Graph

```
net4 <- netmeta(p1, common = FALSE, reference.group = "A")  
netgraph(net4, number = TRUE, points = TRUE, cex.points = 7, adj = 0.5)
```


Smoking Cessation – Network Meta-Analysis

net4

```
## Number of studies: k = 24
## Number of pairwise comparisons: m = 28
## Number of observations: o = 16740
## Number of treatments: n = 4
## Number of designs: d = 8
##
## Random effects model
##
## Treatment estimate (sm = 'OR', comparison: other treatments vs 'A'):
##      OR      95%-CI    z p-value
## A      .           .     .       .
## B 1.52 [0.74; 3.12] 1.13 0.2582
## C 2.08 [1.36; 3.20] 3.35 0.0008
## D 2.47 [1.10; 5.52] 2.19 0.0284
##
## Quantifying heterogeneity / inconsistency:
## tau^2 = 0.5989; tau = 0.7739; I^2 = 88.6% [84.4%; 91.7%]
##
## Tests of heterogeneity (within designs) and inconsistency (between designs):
##              Q d.f.  p-value
## Total              202.62  23 < 0.0001
## Within designs    187.40  16 < 0.0001
## Between designs    15.22   7   0.0333
```

Smoking Cessation – Forest Plot

```
forest(net4, reference.group = c("A", "D"), drop.reference = TRUE,  
label.left = "Favours second intervention",  
label.right = "Favours first intervention")
```


Acute Mania Dataset

```
library("readxl")
AcuteMania <- as.data.frame(read_excel("AcuteMania.xls"))
# Look at some rows
AcuteMania[c(1:3, 102:105), ]
```

```
##      treatment   r   n studyid rob
## 1          ARI 155 253         1  2
## 2          PLA  63 131         1  2
## 3          ARI  72 137         2  2
## 102         PAL 106 195         46  2
## 103         HAL  13  20         47  2
## 104         OLA  53 105         47  2
## 105         PLA  43  99         47  2
```

- Each row contains information for a single treatment arm (long arm-based format): r: number of responders; n: number of patients
- Study 1 is a two-arm study contributing two rows
- Study 47 is a three-arm study contributing three rows
- Use **pairwise** for transformation from long arm-based to contrast-based format

Acute Mania Dataset – Network Meta-Analysis

```
p2 <- pairwise(treat = treatment, event = r, n = n, studlab = studyid,  
data = AcuteMania, sm = "OR")
```

- Mandatory arguments for the long arm-based format and binary outcomes:
treatment labels, number of events, number of participants, **study labels**
- Internally, `metabin` from R package `meta` is called to calculate log odds ratios and corresponding standard errors

```
net5 <- netmeta(p2, ref = "PLA", common = FALSE)
```

- R function `netmeta` can be used directly with R object created with `pairwise`

Acute Mania – Network Graph

```
netgraph(net5, number = TRUE, seq = "optimal", rotate = -360 * (5 / net5$n))
```


Acute Mania Dataset – Forest Plot

forest(net5)

Summary

- Statistical methods for network meta-analysis (NMA) established over the last decade
- Routine use of NMA in medical and other applications
- Main additional assumption of NMA: network consistency
- Next analysis steps, see Balduzzi et al. (2023):
 - Ranking of treatments
 - Generation of league tables
 - Evaluation of inconsistency
- Limitation of R package **netmeta**:
methods for subgroup analysis or network meta-regression missing

References

- Balduzzi, S., Rücker, G., and Schwarzer, G. (2019). How to perform a meta-analysis with R: a practical tutorial. *Evidence-Based Mental Health*, 22(4):153–160.
- Balduzzi, S., Rücker, G., Nikolakopoulou, A., Papakonstantinou, T., Salanti, G., Efthimiou, O., and Schwarzer, G. (2023). netmeta: An R Package for Network Meta-Analysis Using Frequentist Methods. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 106:1–40.
- Bucher, H. C., Guyatt, G. H., Griffith, L. E., and Walter, S. D. (1997). The results of direct and indirect treatment comparisons in meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 50:683–91.
- Cipriani, A., Barbui, C., Salanti, G., Rendell, J., Brown, R., Stockton, S., Purgato, M., Spineli, L. M., Goodwin, G. M., and Geddes, J. R. (2011). Comparative efficacy and acceptability of antimanic drugs in acute mania: a multiple-treatments meta-analysis. *Lancet*, 378(9799):1306–1315.
- Dias, S., Sutton, A. J., Ades, A. E., and Welton, N. J. (2013a). Evidence synthesis for decision making 2: A generalized linear modeling framework for pairwise and network meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Medical Decision Making*, 33:607–617.
- Dias, S., Welton, N. J., Sutton, A. J., Caldwell, D. M., Lu, G., and Ades, A. E. (2013b). Evidence synthesis for decision making 4: Inconsistency in networks of evidence based on randomized controlled trials. *Medical Decision Making*, 33:641–656.
- Higgins, J. P. T., Jackson, D., Barrett, J. K., Lu, G., Ades, A. E., and White, I. R. (2012). Consistency and inconsistency in network meta-analysis: concepts and models for multi-arm studies. *Research Synthesis Methods*, 3(2):98–110.

- Jackson, D., White, I. R., and Riley, R. D. (2013). A matrix-based method of moments for fitting the multivariate random effects model for meta-analysis and meta-regression. *Biometrical Journal*, 55(2):231–245.
- Lu, G., Welton, N. J., Higgins, J. P. T., White, I. R., and Ades, A. E. (2011). Linear inference for mixed treatment comparison meta-analysis: A two-stage approach. *Research Synthesis Methods*, 2(1):43–60.
- Rücker, G. (2012). Network meta-analysis, electrical networks and graph theory. *Research Synthesis Methods*, 3(4):312–324.
- Rücker, G. and Schwarzer, G. (2014). Reduce dimension or reduce weights? Comparing two approaches to multi-arm studies in network meta-analysis. *Statistics in Medicine*, 33:4353–4369.
- Salanti, G. (2012). Indirect and mixed-treatment comparison, network, or multiple-treatments meta-analysis: many names, many benefits, many concerns for the next generation evidence synthesis tool. *Research Synthesis Methods*, 3(2):80–97.
- Senn, S., Gavini, F., Magrez, D., and Scheen, A. (2013). Issues in performing a network meta-analysis. *Statistical Methods in Medical Research*, 22(2):169–189.
- White, I. R., Barrett, J. K., Jackson, D., and Higgins, J. P. T. (2012). Consistency and inconsistency in network meta-analysis: model estimation using multivariate meta-regression. *Research Synthesis Methods*, 3(2):111–125.